

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the second regular issue in 2017. I'd like to thank all members of our editorial board who were involved in the evaluation process of the articles in this issue for their valuable support! I also thank the many reviewers who reviewed papers that did not make it to publication and who thus helped to keep up the high standard of the journal. Finally, I also gratefully acknowledge the support of all institutions and members of the J.UCS consortium for their support.

To further strengthen our editorial board, I'd like to encourage tenured Associate Professors or above with a good publication record to apply for membership in our editorial board. As an open source journal, we offer researchers from all over the world a platform to present scholarship, research, and innovation. Do join us!

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce 3 accepted papers from 5 different countries. In their collaborative research, Aleksei F. Deon from Russia and Yulian A. Menyaev from USA, propose in their work a novel approach to generate complete stochastic sequences which do not need a congruential twisting array, and simulation reveals that received random numbers are distributed absolutely uniformly in the set of unique sequence. In a collaborative work between Spain and Argentina, Maria-Isabel Sanchez-Segura, Fuensanta Medina-Dominguez, Diana-Marcela Vásquez-Bravo, Gustavo Illescas, and Cynthia García de Jesús present a case study analyzing a set of software engineering elicitation techniques. They demonstrate that completeness and preciseness are two criteria to be incorporated into the set of existing parameters used to classify and select which elicitation technique to apply depending on the project context variables. In their paper, Kai Simon, Cornelius Moucha and Joerg Keller from Germany present an alternative approach for vulnerability analysis which applies classical and subject-specific search engines and show its suitability for a timely determination of vulnerabilities in large-scale networks.

Cordially,

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